

Teaching in the New Normal: Accounts From Local College Faculty During COVID 19 Pandemic

Melody Cristie M. Cariño

Abstract. The main objective of this study was to explore and investigate the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights learned by local college instructors in implementing new normal teaching. Qualitative approaches to research phenomenological design from eight Samal Island City College instructors were coded and presented. Three themes in Figure Three were mentioned by the eight (8) selected instructors of Samal Island City College, Samal District, who were the chosen participants for an interview. The themes mentioned in Figure Three were the experiences of the college instructors in implementing new normal teaching, which included feeling bewildered, drawbacks of teaching, and reliance on technology. Meanwhile, the instructors described Figure Four themes as coping mechanisms that included managing time wisely, establishing a personal circle, and seeking help from teacher mentors. These themes were observed during the discussion and described by the respondents. Through their lived experiences and coping strategies, we generate new knowledge in handling the challenges in new normal teaching. Lastly, figure five presents the educational insights learned from the experiences of the college instructors who cited challenging tasks, mentors' love of the profession, and collaboration with other teachers. These themes were generated as insights from local college professors regarding their experiences in implementing the new normal.

KEY WORDS

1. new normal 2. distance learning 3. coping mechanism

Date Received: January 05, 2025 — Date Reviewed: January 15, 2025 — Date Published: February 5, 2025

1. Introduction

As schools have been closed to cope with the global pandemic, students, parents, and educators around the globe have felt the unexpected ripple effect of the COVID-19 pandemic. While governments, frontline workers, and health officials were doing their best to slow down the outbreak, education systems are trying to continue imparting quality education for all during these difficult times. Many students at home/living space have undergone psychological and emotional distress and have been unable to engage productively (Petrie, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic brought extraordinary disruption to higher education (HEI) Institutions, locally and globally. The crisis brought on by the pandemic became a turning point and directed educational institutions to new modalities of instructional implementation. This challenge called for extensive preparation for changes in the educational landscape to ensure that students' learning continued in this new normal in human history. Due to the emergence of COVID-19 in

the Philippines, many changes happened in the educational landscape. One of these was the mode of instruction implemented in the tertiary education. The current COVID-19 pandemic has obliged most education systems to adopt face-to-face teaching and learning alternatives. Many education systems have moved to a distance learning modality to allow instruction to continue despite school closures (OECD, 2020). The shift of the teaching-learning delivery in higher education institutions to distance learning made it more challenging on the part of the instructor in the delivery of tertiary education. Using suitable and relevant pedagogy for online education may depend on educators' and learners' expertise and exposure to information and communications technology (ICT). Some online platforms used so far include unified communication and collaboration platforms such as Microsoft Teams, Google Classroom, Canvas, and Blackboard, allowing teachers to create educational courses, training, and skill development programs (Petrie, 2020). They included workplace chat, video meetings, and file storage options that keep classes organized and easy to work. They usually support sharing content like Word, PDF, Excel files, audio, videos, etc. These also allowed the tracking of student learning and assessment by using quizzes and the rubric-based assessment of submitted assignments. Ministries of education in various countries have recommended or made implementing online learning at all school levels mandatory. This decision has also been supported by UNESCO (2020), which declared that online learning can help stop the spread of the virus by avoiding direct interactions between people. UNESCO (2020) has additionally provided a list of free educational platforms and resources that can be used for online learning according to the needs of each educational institution, providing social care and interaction during school closures. Online learning can be defined as instruction delivered on a digital de-

vice intended to support learning (Clark Mayer, 2016). It is one type of distance learning delivery modality. In the literature, several advantages of online learning have been highlighted: studying from anywhere, at any time; the possibility of saving significant amounts of money; no commuting on crowded buses or local trains; flexibility to choose; and saving time (Nagrале, 2012; Brown, 2017 Bijeesh, 2017). Online learning is thus becoming increasingly important for education during the worldwide health emergency, offering the opportunity to remain in touch, even remotely, with classmates and teachers and to follow lessons. However, many challenges have been observed in different countries. The most evident and widely discussed by experts and policymakers is that socially disadvantaged groups face difficulties meeting the basic conditions required by online learning (Eyles et al., 2020). The following section introduced previous studies on online learning in emergencies. Lockdowns and the subsequent closure of educational institutions have amplified the gap between rich and poor people between the Global North and the Global South and within countries. School closures could hurt learners from lower socioeconomic backgrounds, widening the gap with their more advantaged peers (Montacute, 2020). Indeed, on the one hand, the main objective is safeguarding health, while on the other hand, the aforementioned problems are emerging. According to Hannum et al. (2008), distance learning is a platform that many higher education institutions use to meet the learning needs of students. It has also been determined that distance learning is a practical approach at the college and university level (Hannum et al., 2008; Irvin et al., 2010). When students are required to remain at home, as is the case during the current COVID-19 pandemic, parents need good parenting skills and a good level of education. In addition to monitoring their children's temperament and performance, parents should attempt to satisfy their children's

educational needs as effectively as possible. To respond to the needs of learners, especially of the 3.5 million tertiary-level students enrolled in approximately 2,400 HEIs, certain HEIs in the country have implemented proactive policies for continuing education despite the closure. These policies include modified forms of online learning that aim to facilitate student learning activities. Online learning might include synchronous, real-time lectures and time-based outcomes assessments or asynchronous, delayed-time activities, like pre-recorded video lectures and time-independent assessments (Oztok et al., 2013). Case in point are top universities in the country, viz., De La Salle University (DLSU), Ateneo de Manila University (ADMU), the University of Santo Tomas (UST), and the state-run University of the Philippines, Diliman (UPD). Arguably, the HEIs' pivot to modified forms of online learning attempts to concretize the government's stance to continue learning despite the pandemic. As the Philippines's Department of Education (DepEd) Secretary, Leonor Briones, quipped, "Education must continue even in times of crisis whether it may be a calamity, disaster, emergency, quarantine, or even war" (Department of Education, 2020). The Philippines' Commission on Higher Education (CHED), on the other hand, advised HEIs to continue the "deployment of available flexible learning and other alternative modes of delivery instead of on-campus learning" (Commission on Higher Education, 2020). These pronouncements aim to encourage the continuance of learning. However, private HEIs can make their own policies without implementing rules and regulations. Rural higher education institutions are hit the most by the sudden shift from face-to-face to distance learning modalities because of the limited options and distance between locations. Most rural tertiary institutions in the Davao region shifted to online platforms to continue the students' learning, particularly on Samal Island. We all know that internet connectivity in rural areas is not as widespread as in urban settings, which affects both the students and instructors. In the present scenario, Rural College instructors find adjusting to the sudden shift from face-to-face to online teaching difficult. This study was conceptualized to discover rural college instructors' experiences in the new everyday teaching.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study aimed to unearth and investigate the lived experiences of local college instructors in the new everyday teaching to students. This study was beneficial for administrators, as the data gathered served as research-based information to acquire support from numerous stakeholders by providing them with ideas about the strategies used by local college instructors in the new everyday teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic. This study benefited rural college instructors in understanding and assisting other instructors in using the best practices. Moreover, the focus of this paper examined the experiences of local college instructors in the conduct of the new everyday teaching. Further, the results provided comprehensive data for future research with similar or relevant scope.

1.2. Research Questions—The study intends to get local college instructors' insights and experiences in the new normal teaching. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

- (1) What are the experiences of local college instructors in the new everyday teaching during the pandemic?
- (2) How do the local college instructors cope with the challenges encountered in the new normal teaching during the pandemic?
- (3) What are the educational insights learned from the experiences of local college instructors

in the new everyday teaching during the pandemic?

1.3. *Definition of Terms*—Distance teaching during a pandemic. Teaching delivery was done remotely through online, module, and blended. Online Learning—Online teaching and learning refers to education over the Internet. It is often called distance education or

1.4. *Significant of the Study*—School closures were the universal response to contain the spread of the virus. They shifted to distance learning strategies utilizing online learning platforms for other countries, including the Philippines, to support structures/faculties, students, and their families. However, not all students have the same access to information and communication technologies (ICTs), which varies significantly across countries (OECD, 2020). Furthermore, this study sought to find the local college instructors' coping mechanisms in handling new standard teaching during the pandemic. Therefore, this study would be significant to the following: CHED Officials The study's findings would give them ideas on enhancing local college instructors' capability in the new normal of teaching during the pandemic.

1.5. *Theoretical Lens*—This study is anchored in The Technological Acceptance Model (TAM), which was developed by Davis (1989) and has actual system use (ASU) as the primary variable. Davis defined ASU as an individual's observable usage of a particular system or technology. ASU is a direct function of behavioral intention to use (BIU), a technology that Davis defined as the degree to which a person has formulated conscious plans to perform or not to perform some specific future behavior. BIU is, in turn, a function of attitude toward using (ATU) and perceived usefulness (PU). ATU

web-based education and is currently the latest, most popular form of distance education. Rural College Instructors. College instructors teach classes at local community colleges, technical colleges, and four-year universities. They teach a wide variety of different subjects, depending on their specific field of expertise.

School Administrators

The study findings would guide the school administrators in determining the technical support they should give the rural college instructors in adjusting to the new normal of teaching during the pandemic.

Instructors The study would be significant to them since they would be able to learn about the issues and challenges encountered as they perform the new normal teaching during the pandemic. This would broaden their perspective and understanding of the issues and challenges they are experiencing. Stakeholders This study would be significant to them since it would give stakeholders insights on how to help rural college instructors in the new normal of teaching during the pandemic. Future Researchers The findings provided comprehensive data for future research with similar or relevant scope.

is an individual's positive or negative feeling about performing the target behavior (Davis, Bagozzi Warshaw, 1989), while PU is the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance (Davis, 1989). Accordingly, PU is influenced by perceived ease of use (PEU), which Davis defined as the degree to which a person believes that using a particular technology would be free from effort. Figure 2 further suggests that ATU is determined jointly by PU and PEU. According to TAM theories, external variables such as system characteristics, devel-

opment process, and training influence each PU and PEU. However, other explanatory variables notwithstanding, the proponents of TAM (Davis, 1989) posit that PU and PEU are the two fundamental determinants of ASU. They argue that if users find a helpful technology with PU and is easy to use, such as PEU, they develop a positive attitude toward using it (ATU). All these will eventually lead to the behavioral intention to use (BIU) technology and, finally, the actual use of the technology (ASU). Several researchers have carried out literature reviews on the TAM model. For example, Chuttur's (2009) review provided a historical overview of the TAM in the information system (IS) literature from 1985 to 2007, focusing on its evolution, applications, extensions, limitations, and criticisms. However, he never revealed how he selected the papers for the review and went about the analysis. Regarding findings, however, Chuttur reported that the TAM model was very popular for explaining and predicting system use. However, most of the studies he reviewed had the weakness of only concentrating on self-reported data instead of observed measures, which was a gap for future studies. Also, according to Chuttur (2009), most of the studies he reviewed had focused only on voluntary environments with little consideration for mandatory settings, thus leaving a gap to be filled by future researchers on TAM by extending to mandatory settings. He also found that several studies on the TAM used students as participants. However, according to him, the results obtained from such studies could not be generalized to the real world because students may have peculiar motivations in performing a given behavior (e.g., use of ICT), such as the need to obtain good grades and rewards. Furthermore, Chuttur established that most of the studies he reviewed had been conducted in the US and UK and very few in other parts of the world, particularly in Africa, hence a contextual gap that needed attention by future researchers on the TAM. This study conceptualizes the lived

experiences of local college instructors in new everyday teaching during the pandemic. Local college instructors encountered challenges during the early stages, but this could be addressed through the constant support and assistance of other faculty in daily activities. Identify the lesson learned on the effective conduct of new everyday teaching during the pandemic. Both aim to provide information on the experiences of local college instructors in new everyday teaching, perspectives, and challenges during a pandemic. The data collected during the virtual interviews was transcribed, organized, and reviewed in searching for patterns and themes. Because this study involved human participants, informed consent was secured for ethical purposes. The instructor's experiences were explored using semi-structured in-depth interviews after signing consent forms. Data was organized, and the procedures were undertaken to analyze the textual data. Collected transcripts were listened to and transcribed with a list of significant statements developed from the transcripts and grouped into larger units of information called "meaning tunings" or themes (Creswell, 2007). With the list of non-redundant units of meaning, the researcher must continue bracketing any assumptions to remain faithful to the phenomenon (Groenewald, 2004). The researcher rigorously examined these units of meaning to elicit the essence of meaning within the holistic context. Clusters of themes are typically formed by grouping units of meaning (Creswell, 1998). He further described by writing a description with the structural description of how the experience happened, reflecting on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced (Creswell, 2007). Finally, a composite description of the phenomenon was written; this is the essence of the experience and represents the culmination of the phenomenological study (Creswell, 2007). Figure 1 shows the interconnection between the two research questions, the best practices based on the Lived

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

experiences of local college instructors in new everyday teaching during a pandemic and their challenges during the trying times or hardship in handling classes, while the second circle was their coping strategy. Moreover, the intersection served as the common denominator and

2. Methodology

This chapter presents the method, research participants, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. Exploring facts and knowledge in this study necessitated the consequent design and implementation, as elaborated in this chapter. The three most common qualitative methods are participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals' histories, perspectives, and experiences, mainly when exploring sensitive topics. Focus groups effectively elicit data on a group's cultural norms and generate broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as inquiry that asks the question, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" "the goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand the experiences of the BE Coordinators as they try to compare its implementation then and now. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation greater in depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested that information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption is a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used to reach conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research begins with the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (1987) traces ‘paradigm’ back to its Greek (paradigm) and Latin origins (paradigm), meaning pattern, model, or example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions are taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was an action of submitting to a view. This view was supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who defend a research paradigm as a “basic set of beliefs that guide action,” dealing with first principles, “ultimates” or the researcher’s worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multiple, as seen by the study participants. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. The reality was constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the experiences of rural college instructors in new normal teaching during the pandemic were discussed by the participants, and they tried to look into their strategies in addressing the challenges and educational insights. In this study, the researcher relied on voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes, themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The answers of the participants to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct for the commonality and discreteness of responses. It was made sure that the responses of the participants were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progresses. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln as cited by Creswell (2012) state that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen the distance between himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that being a researcher he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an ‘insider’. Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). Researcher identified phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers “hold explicit belief”. The intention of this study was to gather information from the participants or college instructors in Samal Island City College, Samal District as to how to implement new everyday teaching based on the guidelines set by DepEd and the Inter Agency Task Force (IATF). It was assured that there was an establishment of close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the experiences and coping mechanism used in new normal teaching. Axiology. It refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2012) avers that the role of values in a study was significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. Upholding the dignity and value of every detail of information obtain from the participants was ensured by the researcher. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of information gathered from the study. Therefore, the researcher preserved the merit of the participants’ answers and care-

fully interpret the answers in the light of the participants' interpretation. Rhetoric. It means that reporting what reality was through the eyes of the research participants. This was important because it means that the research would report objectively on what was observed and

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—Methodology was different from method. Methodology was creative and responsive approach to understand questions and subject matter while method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study the challenges experienced by the local college instructors in new normal teaching during COVID 19 pandemic in Samal District were gathered through an In-Depth Interview (IDI) as well as the coping mechanisms were extracted from the participants. The researcher's drive in knowing the deeper meaning of the challenges experienced by rural area instructors in new normal teaching became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means of which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias, (2013) considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences and phenomena". By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the challenges experienced by rural area instructors in new normal teaching in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote, the themes,

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study employed a qualitative approach to research specifically a phenomenological research design. According to Creswell, (2012), phenomenology was an approach to qualitative research that focused on the commonality of lived experiences within a particular group. The fundamental goal of the approach was to arrive at a description of the nature of the particular phenomenon. Typically, interviews were con-

heard from the participants. The research used personal voice and qualitative terms and limited definition. In the context of the study, the researcher used the first person in elucidation of the experiences of teachers as they adapt new normal teaching during COVID 19 pandemic.

symbols and meaning of the experiences presented. Phenomenological research was based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs, (2006), that experience was a source of knowledge and shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world is a valuable and productive source of knowledge, and that we can learn much about ourselves and reap key insights into the nature of an event by analyzing how it occurs in our daily lives (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). By doing phenomenology which concerns with that "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher projected that the challenges experienced, coping mechanisms used by the rural area instructors were explored and insights drawn as the basis for the possible future researches and policy analysis in relation to this research.

ducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation or experience. Other forms of data such as documents, observations and art were also used. The data were read and reread and was culled for phrases and themes that was grouped into clusters of meanings. Through this process, the researcher was able to construct the universal meaning of the event, situation or experience and arrived at a more profound understanding

of the phenomenon. Moreover, Maxwell (2013) also added that with the roots in philosophy, psychology and education, phenomenology attempt to extract the purest, untainted data and in some interpretations of the approach, bracketing were used by the researcher to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or herself from the process. One method of bracketing is taking of notes. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design was a qualitative type of research for which interviews provide in-depth method that can grant access to deep knowledge and explanations and help grasp the subjects' perspective. Creswell, (2012) also claimed that interviews were primarily done in qualitative research and occur when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. Often audio tapes were utilized to allow more consistent transcription. Interviews also useful to follow-up with individual respondents after questionnaires, such as to further investigate their responses. In qualitative research, interviews were used to pursue the meanings of central themes in the world of their subjects. The main task in doing interviews was to understand the meaning of what the interviewees say (McNamara, 1999). Withal, based on the statements of Quad (2016), the researcher transcribed and typed the data into a computer file, in order to analyze it after interviewing. Interviews particularly be useful for uncovering the story behind a participant's experiences and pursuing in-depth information around a topic. The researcher collected data, typically via long interviews, from individuals who have experienced the phenomenon under investigation. Next, the data analysis involved triangulation that was extracted significant statements from

the transcribed interviews. The significant statements were transformed into clusters of meanings according to how each statement fell under specific psychological and phenomenological concepts. Moreover, these transformations were tied up together to make a general description of the experience both the textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated his or her personal meaning of the experiences here. Finally, the report was written such that readers understand better the essential, invariant structure of the essence of the experience. Conversely, several challenges have been pointed out. The researcher required a solid grounding in the philosophical guidelines of phenomenology. The subjects that were selected into the study were individuals who have actually experienced the phenomenon. The researcher needed to bracket his or her own experiences and observations, which was difficult to do. The researcher also needed to decide as to how and when his or her personal observations be incorporated into the study. Epistemologically, phenomenological approaches was based on the paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity, and emphasize the importance of personal perspective and interpretation. As such they were powerful tools for understanding subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and actions, and cutting through the cluster of taken-for-granted assumptions and conventional wisdom Since the focus of this study to explore and asses the teacher experience and feelings towards the school environment and on the perspectives of the seasoned teachers, the researcher would intend to employ the phenomenology type of qualitative method research.

2.4. Research Participants—The participants of this study were Eight (8) teachers from Samal District, Division of Island Garden City

of Samal. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: (1) must be in the service for at least 3 years; (2) local college instruc-

tor; and (3) experienced new normal teaching. The researcher utilized the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell, 2014). It was also known as judgmental, selec-

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—The ethical considerations are significant in the design of this research study. The researcher needed to consider several ethical issues about the research participant in this fieldwork. Ethical considerations can be specified as one of the most important parts of the research. The researcher needs to adhere to promote the aims of the research imparting authentic knowledge, truth and prevention of error.

Social Value Research was very essential to the society. In this study, the social value was focused on the experienced of teachers. This study was specifically conducted among the elementary teachers. This study also served as a basis for the higher authorities to create more programs and resolutions where classroom teacher could benefit. Thus, the social problem that pushes the interest of the researcher is the challenges faced by the teachers in the use of interactive media instruction in the classroom as a way to ameliorate teaching competence.

Informed Consent In the conduct and practice of this study, the Treaty Principle of Participation as cited by McLeod (2009) adhered to. The invitation to the participants was ensured that their participation in the research was completely voluntary in nature, and is based on the understanding of adequate information. The participant recruitment and selection lodged in the appendices of this study. Gaining the trust and support of research participants was critical to the informed and ethical academic inquiry and phenomenological research (Walker, 2007 as cited by Pillerin, 2012). All participants were given an informed consent form before scheduling the interviews and participating in the phe-

nomological research process. Each participant was required to provide a signed personal acknowledgement, consent, and an indication of a willingness-to-participate-in-the-study-release. The purpose of the informed consent letter is to introduce the research effort, provide contact information, articulate the intent of the study, request voluntary participation by the recipients, and anticipate the information that the informants were expected to provide. All participants were required to sign and return the letter of consent to the researcher before participating in the research.

Vulnerability of Research Participants The participants of this study were capable of answering the research instrument for they are all professional teachers in public elementary schools. Thus, the researcher assured them that as the researcher, he or she can easily be reached through the contact number and address in case there are some clarifications or questions with regard to the study.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety
The recruitment of the respondents was free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the panel chair or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. Furthermore, if respondents experienced potential discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelling to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the questionnaire was distributed in a safe venue and administered at a convenient time. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Prin-

principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This was done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality.

Privacy and Confidentiality of Information
This study observed the Data Privacy Act of 2002 to ensure that the data cannot be traced back to their actual sources to protect participants' identities. Thus, utmost care was taken to ensure the anonymity of the data sources. Hence, any printed output that was carried out from this study was kept in anonymity. Furthermore, all the issues were considered so there would be no conflict of interest among the researcher and the respondents. Any misleading information and representation of primary data findings in a biased way must be avoided. Justice The respondents were informed of the researcher's role and their corresponding role during data gathering. They were briefed that they had to answer the survey questions honestly, and they should also be honest in any communication related to the research. Similarly, they were informed that they were the ones to benefit first from the study's results.

Transparency The respondents accessed the results of the study, heads of the participating schools because the information was available and was placed on CD or other storage devices which can be requested from the researcher to provide. In addition, by learning about the results of the study, classroom teachers were aware of the significance of the study and its contribution to their well-being. Further, each of the participants was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they can be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview is carried out. This provided the partici-

pants with the opportunity to amend, or remove any information which they feel might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms and change names and/or non-significant dates in the interest of protecting the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting.

Qualification of the Researcher

The researcher ensured that he or she possesses the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher should have completed the academic requirements and passed the comprehensive examination prior to thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the master's degree, and the researcher should be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion.

Adequacy of Facilities The researcher strived that the study can be completed successfully in the specified time and that he or she is equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee helped enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations for the improvement of the study. Also, the researcher ensured that he or she had enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, it was hoped that this study would be completed within the target time. **Community Involvement** The researcher showed respect for the local traditions, culture, and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study did not involve any use of deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in the recruitment of the participants or methods of data collection. Furthermore, the researcher necessarily expressed great pleasure in the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study.

Plagiarism And Fabrication as The Researcher The researcher respected other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else has said in his or her own way.

The researcher also used quotes to indicate that the text had been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher assured that honesty was present in working on the manuscript, and no

intentional misrepresentation or making up of data or results was included or purposefully put forward conclusions that were not accurate.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—The researcher was responsible for uncovering, transferring, and exploiting knowledge for the benefit of educational institutions. To do so, the researcher takes up the following roles in the course of the study: Facilitator and Promoter of Unbiased Research. The researcher conducts interviews with the participants and guides them in the process. The researcher interprets ideas and responses based on existing literature and related studies and not on the researcher's own knowledge, thoughts, and feelings to avoid the intrusion of bias. Expert in qualitative methods. The researcher implements the qualitative method correctly. To do so, the researcher assesses himself and seeks help from the research adviser and other research professionals. These help him exhibit competence in explaining the study without biasing the participants, conducting interviews properly according to the design, making appropriate field observations, selecting appropriate artifacts, images, and journal portions, and employing Environmental Triangulation and Thematic Content Analysis precisely. Collector and Keeper of data. The researcher ensures different ways of making a record of what is said and done during the interview and

Focus Group Discussion, such as taking handwritten notes or audio and/or video recording. The recordings are transcribed verbatim before data analysis can begin. Records done by the researcher are adequately secured as they contain sensitive information and are relevant to the research. However, the data are being collected, and the researcher's primary responsibility was to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins. Data analyst. The researcher sees the phenomenon or problem from the participants' perspective by interpreting data, transcribing and checking, reading between the lines, coding, and theming. The researcher ensures that the findings are true to the participants and their voices are heard. The researcher organizes and presents data. The researcher presents the problem and the related literature and studies that support it. The study's findings are presented, too, by the research question, stating the results for each one using themes to show how the research questions were answered in the study. Moreover, the researcher gives future directions and implications of the study for improving educational policy and practices.

2.7. Data Collection—To ensure safe educational continuity admits the challenge of COVID-19, this study adhered to the Department of Health (DOH) Administrative Order No. 2020-0015 or the Guidelines on the Risk-Based Public Health Standards for COVID-19 Mitigation, cited by the IATF to aid all sectors in all settings to implement non-pharmaceutical

interventions. The following is the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher would send a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with Chapters

1 and 2 attached, together with the research instrument explaining the objectives of the study and identifying the participants. The researcher would wait for the response of the SDS before conducting the study. Asking permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher sent letters to the principals of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. The researcher asked permission from the participants and their parents/guardians. They were formally oriented about the study and the process they would undergo as participants. Conducting the interview. The researcher conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taken, notes were jotted down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher analyzed the answers of the participants from the conducted interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis. The researcher immersed herself in and became intimately familiar with their data, reading and re-reading it and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, involving generating pithy labels for important features of the data relevant to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a data reduction method but also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and

researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. The researcher transcribed the interviewees' responses precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants used their vernacular language, the researcher translated it into English. Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis. After the transcription, the data would then be categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual data within the participants was compared and contrasted. The researcher then conducted a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants; additional information gathered was examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants to develop patterns and trends.

relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher reflected on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and began to define the nature of each theme and the relationship between the themes. Thematic Content Analysis was employed by the researcher for these. Thematic Content Analysis was a descriptive presentation of qualitative data in which a detailed analysis of each theme was made by identifying the 'essence' of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy and informative name for each theme (Andersen, 2013). In addition, to enhance validity and to create a more in-depth picture of the phenomenon, the researcher also employed Environmental Triangulation. It was a technique to analyze the same study's results using different data collection methods. The key was identifying which environmental factors might influence the informa-

tion received during the study. These environmental factors are changed to see if the findings are the same across the settings (David, 2015). This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors such as time, day, and season in which the study occurred. The idea was to determine which of these factors influenced the information received, and these factors were then changed to see if the findings were the same. Validity can be established if the findings remain unaltered under varying en-

vironmental factors (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement, as mentioned, was the use of environmental triangulation best suited to the environment of the research being conducted. Writing up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it in relation to existing literature.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The framework analysis of this research was flexible to allow the researcher to either collect all the data and then analyze it or do data analysis during the collection process. In the analysis stage, the gathered data was sifted, charted, and sorted by key issues and themes. This involves a five-step process: (1) familiarization, (2) identifying a thematic framework, (3) indexing, (4) charting, and (5) mapping and interpretation (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Familiarization refers to the process during which the researcher becomes familiarized with the transcripts of the data collected (i.e., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, or field notes) and gains an overview of the collected data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). In other words, the researcher becomes immersed in the data by listening to audiotapes, studying the field, or reading the transcripts. Throughout this process, the researcher will become aware of key ideas and recurrent themes and make a note of them. Due to the sheer volume of data that can be collected in qualitative research, the researcher may not be able to review all of the material. Thus, a selection of the data set would be utilized. The selection would depend on several aspects of the data collection process. For example, the mix of methods used (e.g., interviews, documents, observations), Identifying a thematic framework, the second stage, occurs after familiarization when

the researcher recognizes emerging themes or issues in the data set. These emerging themes or issues may have arisen from a priori themes are issues however it was at this stage that the researcher must allow the data to dictate the themes and issues. To achieve this end the researcher uses the notes taken during the familiarization stage. The key issues, concepts and themes that have been expressed by the participants now form the basis of a thematic framework that can be used to filter and classify the data (Ritchie Spencer, 1994). Indexing means that one identifies portions or sections of the data that correspond to a particular theme. This process is applied to all the textual data that has been gathered (i.e. transcripts of interviews). For the sake of convenience Ritchie and Spencer recommend that a numerical system be used for the indexing references and annotated in the margin beside the text (1994). Qualitative data analysis tools are ideal for such a task. The final stage, mapping and interpretation, involves the analysis of the key characteristics as laid out in the charts. This analysis should be able to provide a schematic diagram of the event/phenomenon thus guiding the researcher in their interpretation of the data set. It was at this point that the researcher was cognizant of the objectives of qualitative analysis, which are: “defining concepts, mapping range and nature of phenomena, creating typologies, finding associ-

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

ations, providing explanations, and developing strategies” (Ritchie and Spencer, 1994). Once again, these concepts, technologies, and associations are reflective of the participant. Therefore, any strategy or recommendations made by the researcher echo the true attitudes, beliefs, and

values of the participants. Figure 2 illustrates the stages of the study’s analytical framework, which includes familiarization, coding, creating a thematic framework, indexing, charting, mapping, and interpretation.

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In qualitative study, trustworthiness was very important because the result and finding of

the research study would depend on the process of how it was being conducted by the researcher. The trustworthiness of a research study is important to evaluate its worth. Due to the nature of the qualitative study, honesty in all the data

and details is required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher's study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. Credibility The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do was essential to attain worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues that ruin her integrity. Lincoln and Guba (2000) state that credibility refers to the idea of internal consistency, where the main issue was "how we ensure rigor in the research process and how we communicate to others that we have done so."

Transferability Qualitative researcher demonstrates that the research study's findings are applicable to other contexts. In this case, "other contexts" can mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. The researcher has already studied the effects of using graphic organizers as a strategy for teaching reading comprehension. The use of graphic organizers as a strategy in teaching reading comprehension is effective in the domains of analysis and creation. With this, the researcher is interested in the students' perspective on using this strategy. Gasson (2004) emphasizes transferability as the extent to which the reader was able to provide generalization of the study based on his context and can able to address that core issue of "how far a researcher may make claims for a general application of the theory."

Confirmability The degree of neutrality in the research study's findings. In other words, this means that the findings are based on partici-

pants' responses and not the researcher's potential bias or personal motivations. This involves ensuring that researcher bias does not skew the interpretation of what the research participants said to fit a particular narrative. The information used in the audit trail in this situation is thoughtfully recorded by the researcher, which highlights every step of data analysis that was made in order to provide a rationale for the decisions made. This helps establish that the research study's findings accurately portray participants' responses. Gasson (2004) states that confirmability was based on the acknowledgment that research is never objective. **Dependability** The extent to which other researchers could repeat the study and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher uses an inquiry audit to establish dependability, which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis to ensure that the findings are consistent and can be repeated. In this component, a database was essential in backing up information collected and noting changes for all research studies. All the data collected was kept correctly for future use as references. Gasson (2004) stated that dependability deals with the core issue of "how a study is conducted should be consistent across time, researchers, and analysis techniques."

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from analyzing the interview data. It presents themes that emerged from the analysis, along with comprehensive discussions that answer the study's objectives. The result primarily presents the description and background of the participants who were assigned pseudonyms to conceal their identities.

3.1. Experiences Of Local College Instructors Teaching in The New Normal—Ever since the pandemic, the education system has been

widely affected. The COVID-19 pandemic has caused widespread disruptions to schools and universities. According to UNESCO, as of

April 10, 2020, more than 188 countries had implemented nationwide school and university closures, impacting over 91 of the world's student population (UNESCO). During these school closures, all face-to-face lessons were cancelled, compelling many institutions, including universities to immediate transition from face-to-face in-person learning to completely online lessons. The abrupt switch to online learning has been particularly stressful for many instructors and students who prefer in-person instruction. Online learning is often stigmatized as a weaker option that provides a lower quality education than in-person face-to-face learning (Hodges et al. 2020). With the new normal, DepEd designed

the Basic Education–Learning Continuity Plan. This plan aims to ensure the safety of students, teachers, and staff. It also intends to give quality distance learning by using self-learning modules. These can be accessed through digital forms, radio, TV, and online platforms; however, many struggle to engage in online teaching, especially those without stable internet access, and resources are left behind. It was a big challenge for the education department to carry out its current functions. For some teachers, those challenges were in addition to an already tricky transition into their years of teaching (Canonizado, 2020).

3.1.1. Feeling bewildered—In the in-depth interview of the participants, it was revealed that their experiences of bewilderment were common. The clearest theme to emerged came as no surprise to anyone; teachers were bewildered by the challenge of transitioning actual school to school-supported home learning. There were many elements that contributed to the feeling of surprise that teachers described as changing methods of delivery, uncertainty about the duration of the home learning, unclear expectations for instruction, Logistical complications of acquiring and distributing learning resources to students amidst a highly contagious pandemic, The need to utilize previously unused technologies and the pressures of bewildered parents and families (Canonizado, 2020). Given all of those demands and complexities, it is evident that teachers' emotions and attitudes were most significantly impacted. Participants were interviewed two and three months after their schools had closed their doors to in-person teaching.

Many of the issues identified above had to be addressed to keep the school going; however, even after the school year ended, the emotions remained (Canonizado, 2020). According to Whitcomb, Borko, and Liston (2008), even when equipped with excellent teacher education, teachers are still required to learn and develop pedagogical skills, content knowledge, and workplace culture familiarity on their feet while assuming this new regular responsibility for dozens of children. Several participants articulated that they had just begun to feel comfortable, to get in their groove, as one teacher put it when the pandemic hit. They had worked through online classroom management failures and built cooperative relationships with other school personnel and students. Three participants identified how much they were looking forward to seeing end-of-year test scores as evidence of the growth they felt they and their students had achieved. The experience of transitioning from their now more comfortable classrooms to online teaching was unsettling.

3.1.2. Drawback of teaching—The participants' in-depth virtual interviews revealed their answers' commonality. The experience of ex-

haustion and other factors are part of the drawbacks of teaching in the new regular classroom. It was validated by Ferdig et al. (2020) as

they posited that exhaustion, due to lack of time for the preparation of modules and performing teaching-related tasks such as the design and development of instructional materials, was the dominant theme. This experience was considered a drawback because extreme fatigue was not unlikely to occur if you have love and commitment in your teaching career, especially if the occurrence was something beyond the teacher's control. If teaching is mentally and emotionally draining, then this condition could overflow into the learning environment in which the health and wellness of teachers are supposed to prevail to shape and mold the students properly (Ferdig et al., 2020). This phenomenon was validated by Gavish Friedman (2010), who found that teachers experience drawbacks when they are no longer happy with what they are

3.1.3. Reliance on technology—In the participants' in-depth interview, it was common in their responses of the reliance on technology usage in the new normal classroom. Teachers reported feeling significant advantages in this pandemic. They almost all reported experiencing an advantage for the very same reason. These teachers had been recently exposed to different online learning platforms during their teacher education training. These participants consistently cited that familiarity as an advantage. It was much easier for teachers to teach online with varying online strategies. However, then for the older teachers, it was a more significant adjustment for them (Canonizado, 2020). Additionally, the teacher education program from which these teachers have recently graduated required all students to take a course focused on using technology in the classroom. Many teachers specifically named the value of the things they learned in that course – mainly if they had already applied them by introducing students to new technologies for learning – helping them successfully transition their instruction

doing. The participants did not directly attribute burnout to insufficient time to prepare for teaching tasks. Instead, their participants indicated that burnout was, among others, due to an unappreciative social environment. This situation may have contributed to the drawback teachers felt in this study. In any case, the drawback of teaching as a lived experience cannot be taken as an isolated experience. The contributing factors were seen in the other parts of teachers' narrations, such as multiple tasks resulting in an enormous amount of work, teaching or nonteaching-related. Thus, when exhaustion occurs due to insufficient time to prepare, along with many things related to teaching, research, or community work, all of these put together could lead to weariness (Ferdig et al., 2020).

to online formats. Participants cited this recent technology education as giving them an advantage and making them new valuable members of their school teams, able to provide helpful instructional support to their colleagues (Canonizado, 2020). Here are transcripts of participants of this in-depth- interview as presented below: Attentive students of public schooling in the United States have long identified the impact of differential resource distribution on schools (Cochran-Smith Fries, 2005; Holme Rangel, 2012). The impact of the pandemic is no different—resource distribution matters to students' educational achievement and teachers' working conditions. Student engagement was one of the most evident measures related to resource distribution. Only one participant reported that all her students engaged in the school fully supported home learning throughout 2020. The figure above shows the experiences of local college instructors in the new normal. Three themes emerged from the participants' responses: feeling bewildered, the drawbacks of teaching, and reliance on technology.

Fig. 3. Emerging Themes On Experiences Of Local College Instructors In The New Normal

3.2. *Coping Mechanisms Used by The Teachers In Dealing With the Challenges in The New Normal—*

The current COVID-19 pandemic is suddenly and dramatically transforming ways of working, living, and relating to each other globally. Higher education institutions were undergoing radical transformations driven by the need to digitalize education and training processes in record time, with academics lacking innate technological capabilities for online teaching. (Krishnamurthy, 2020). Most often, teachers used more functional coping strategies when they expected factors as barriers to teaching. As an educator, one way to overcome the barriers is to make the learners aware of the current situation and the method used in teaching. In addition, having mutual understanding with the learners

can create a connection between the learners and the teachers (Marcelo, 2009). In addition, Dwivedi et al. (2020) said that the reality of the new normal, disrupted by COVID-19 effects, has involved a sudden transformation of education and training, and one of the sectors undergoing dramatic digital transformation is global higher education. This transformation is not obstacle-free, and some barriers and challenges emerged in this process. To enable safe transition and achieve a successful transformation, universities must be aware of these potential obstacles and establish appropriate mechanisms to overcome them. (Marinoni et al., 2020; Mishra et al., 2020).

3.2.1. Managing time wisely—It was revealed during the in-depth virtual interview of the rural college instructors that time management was an important practice to meet the demands of home and work. Participants said that time management helped them to accomplish things on time. This lets them attend school duties, do household chores, and regain energy through rest. Establishing routines through habits and practices in a set schedule helps them to utilize time efficiently. Also, taking advantage of tools and technology to perform works like submission of outputs, computation of scores, checking of written works and delivery of instruction provides comfort and convenience (Raines, 2011). Time management behavior was characterized as a worthwhile thing that requires it to be managed efficiently and acts as a key indicator of managerial economic edge (Rutte Roe, 2007). Management of time describes those behaviors that aim

to accomplish an operative time usage in acting on definite life-orienting actions (Claessens, 2007). Many professions have high demands on individuals' time. Britton and Glynn (1989) inferred them as rationally productive individuals who usually possess some extra things necessary to perform the tasks within a specific time span. Now, such professions have become more creative ways to complete different job-related activities even in the scarcity of time and other resources. The individual that gives great attention to their tasks always shows higher outcomes. Better time management will enhance the worker's productivity and enables them to work in smarter ways (Green Skinner, 2005). Likewise, Jamal (1984) studied that effective time management reduces job stress and increases the job performance of employees. Claessens (2004) acknowledged that better time management give more control of individual to his time and resultantly decreases the work anxiety and higher the job performance.

3.2.2. Establishing Professional Circles—In the in-depth virtual interview of instructors regarding their coping mechanism was about

building professional learning circles. Your relationships with others will keep you strong, and they fuel your energy to persist through

challenges. Build strong relationships with your colleagues and administrators and with your students and their parents. If you're shy, now was the time to pick up some strategies to make connections with others. Ask questions, knock on doors, and invite people into your classroom. Your community is a lift when times get hard. Grant (2006) and Levine (2011) believe teachers develop and evolve into Teacher Professional Communities; these communities exist by having norms, routines, and shared vision. Teacher communities evolve naturally and help understand positive and negative student and staff outcomes (Levine, 2011). Teacher's professional communities exist in educational settings and have a positive impact depending on the culture within the learning community. They play an intricate role in professional development. Organizational goals and vision provide the foundation necessary for professional growth to occur. Gallucci, Van Lare, Yoon, and Boatright (2010) believe professional learning must be coordinated across people, settings, and events. Teacher performance and student outcomes should be the shared responsibility by educators (Louis, Marks, Kruse, 1996). A study analyzed data collected through the Na-

tional Center for Educational Statistics (NCES, 2011) and determined schools organized with a strong commitment strategy have better success in achieving their goals. Increased teacher participation in content-related professional development and greater stability in teaching staff result in increased learning outcomes. Barrier, Anson, Ording, and Evelyn (2002) found that all initiatives should be tailored to the specific context of the organization. Employees should be engaged in the process of defining initiatives, and high levels of leadership commitment must be maintained for adult learning to occur. Professional learning communities work begin with guiding principles set through the process of norm development (Dumay, 2009; Thoonen et al., 2011; Timperley Alton-Lee, 2008). Norms guide team members in working collaboratively through clarifying expectations on how individuals will collectively work together to achieve shared goals (DuFour, 2010). Team norms provide the structure, approach, and culture for "doing business." Levine (2011) promoted norms that include collaboration, shared objectives, respect for experienced teachers, and promotion of morale.

3.2.3. *Seeking help from teacher mentors*—Instructional coaching and mentoring were tools for professional growth and learning. Zellers, Howard, and Barcic (2008) refer to the network of support for professional growth as "constellations." Luna and Cullen (1995) refer to this structure as mosaics of supportive relationships. A qualitative (Gallucci et al., 2010) study within three urban districts implemented a coaching program where coaches learned right alongside those being coached, making the process dynamic. The design implemented specific coaching within a team of first-grade teachers interested in improving reading outcomes. Gallucci et al. (2010) recognized that coaches were conduits for reform, taking information and dis-

seminating it within their district. This coaching approach created a symbiotic relationship where learning was done between coach and teacher (Cuddapah Clayton, 2011). This relationship allowed learning to circulate to and with others. Coaches also allowed teachers to participate in observations of other professionals. One professional development model integrated coaching within the context of teacher preparation. The figure above shows the coping mechanisms used by the local college instructors in dealing with the challenges of the new normal during the pandemic. Three themes emerged from the participants' responses: managing time wisely, establishing a professional circle, and seeking help from teacher mentors.

Fig. 4. Emerging Themes On The Coping Mechanisms Used By The Local College Instructors In The New Normal Teaching During Pandemic

3.3. *Educational Insights Drawn from The Study*—A year ago, the global pandemic turned educational institutions upside down. Suddenly, travel was limited or canceled ultimately. Teachers who had never worked remotely worked from home for the first time, sometimes while juggling household responsibilities. Workplace connections that had occurred casually in the faculty room or in the office corridor were no more, and meetings were held virtually. Here are some of the educational insights from the study.

3.3.1. *Challenging task*—According to Ramsden, P. (2003) teaching in higher education is a challenging task because lesson content should be based on research and theories in order to create and develop the student’s scientific competence. The education shall offer a relevant content and teaching, managing a critical and analyzing competence. It means that the content or the experience should be challenged and problematized with a grounding in theory and research (Ramsden, 2003). Considering the goal of higher education to stimulate the student’s capacity for a critical analytical approach and the importance of this in teaching practices, this pose stimulating task to the teachers. Knight Yorke, (2003) further added that the academic professional education needs to be formed from an idea of what it is that contributes to a learning environment that creates the conditions for the skills requirements formulated for the profession. According to Lam, (2020) pandemic has presented an opportunity for rethinking assumptions about education in general and higher education in particular. In light of the general crisis, teaching educators from all grades and contexts experienced the

necessity of rethinking their roles, the ways of supporting the student's learning tasks, and the image of students as self-organizing learners, active citizens, and autonomous social agents.

3.3.2. Mentors love the profession—Based on Smeed and Jetnikoff (2016), teachers laud the benefits of having connections and collegial discussion schemes to achieve sustainability. Teachers shared that meeting new people and sharing with them the togetherness in the virtual room or making new friends is a driving force behind the successful construction of knowledge and part of our pandemic survival. The love of profession and learning, in general, was a concept that people in many different ways can use, can be liberating, as teachers who are learners too feel power and capacity to understand, discover, and grasp truth' (Nilsen 2004), these being capabilities previously not imagined for discovering knowledge for themselves. For the teachers, getting your students excited about topics you love is just one way you can share a love of learning, you'll also get to delve into new topics and learn right along with the children. You'll also have the chance to become a student again. As emerging technologies and instructional methods are introduced, and historic events unfold in real-time, you'll always be learning something new.(Kansas University, Online Blog 2021) Teachers being mentors can make a real difference in the lives of

the children they will one day teach. Each day that you work with students, you have the potential to make a lasting impression. Almost all of can remember something positive that one of our teachers said to us or the class as a whole. There were lessons that stuck in our minds and impacted our viewpoints for years. Becoming a teacher means molding future generations through the curriculum you set and bits of personal wisdom you impart. You will have the ability and power to teach life lessons and core subjects. There is a good chance that you may be spending more waking hours with these children than their parents. This means you will be the one to help teach them social skills, time management, conflict resolution, coping with stressors, and focusing on a task(Dawd M, 2018). When teachers connect the interests, backgrounds, ideas, and strengths of each individual, it can contribute to the success of the school. If teachers work in a team, they can delegate tasks according to the personality and expertise of each team member. This type of teamwork contributes to a greater sense of trust and accountability, and it allows teachers to feel confident about contributing their most dynamic skills and application of their learnings toward school improvement.

3.3.3. Collaboration with other teachers—It was revealed during the in-depth interview of the teachers that the commonality of their answers was that collaboration with co-teachers was beneficial. According to Burns, Vanderwood, and Ruby (2005), collaboration allows for varied expertise and perspectives to be shared among each other. This collective expertise provides collaborators with a more comprehensive understanding of the needs of

individuals, which can be used to plan and prepare for improvement effectively. Teachers use respectful and practical communication skills as they collaborate with others. Collaboration is broadly recommended in education for accomplishing a wide range of goals, delivering instruction, ensuring support through professionals, and resolving student and programmatic issues (Burns, Vanderwood, Ruby, 2005). However, collaboration is ethereal in that it is never

an end in itself; instead, it operates as a culture or a means to reach any goal. Collaboration is often indirectly fostered among members of a school work group by arranging time for participants to meet face-to-face, guiding them through the development of positive professional relationships, establishing explicit and implicit procedures for working together, and teaching them about school programs that rely on collaborative interactions (e.g., teams, co-teaching). Collaboration, in research generally has found strong support among teachers, but mixed results for students (Murawski Swanson, 2001; Scruggs, Mastropieri, McDuffie, 2007). It is working closely to coordinate the delivery of learning materials and resources such as time to plan, hence, small positive effects on student academic outcomes are achieved (Sollis, Vaughn, Swanson, McCulley, 2012). A related study supported this conclusion, finding that teachers who collaborate made significant progress in their work, while those who work in separate settings did not; the gap between the

two groups was widening over time (Tremblay, 2013). Figure 5 shows the educational insights the local college instructors learned in implementing the new normal during a pandemic. Three themes emerged from the responses of the participants: challenging tasks, mentors' love of the profession, and collaboration with other teachers. These themes implied that being a teacher is a challenging task because, as educators, they experienced the necessity of rethinking their roles, the ways of supporting the student's learning tasks, and the image of students as active citizens and autonomous social agents. Also, mentors love of profession. The love of profession and learning is a concept that mentors can use in many different ways; establishing connections with friends and colleagues who understand circumstances can help teachers deal with rigorous tasks. Likewise, collaboration with other teachers provides collaborators with a more comprehensive understanding of the needs of individuals, which can be used to plan and prepare for improvement effectively.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presented a brief overview of the study followed by implications based on the findings. Future directions in the field of teachers' experiences were also discussed here.

4.1. Findings—The study aimed to explore local college instructors' experiences while implementing the new regular—teaching during a pandemic. Three themes were drawn in each of the phenomena in the conceptual framework of this study. Regarding the experiences of college instructors in the study, three themes emerged from the responses of the participants: feeling bewildered, the drawbacks of teaching, and reliance on technology. This theme implies that teaching is a mixture of challenges, surprises, fun, and excitement. Meanwhile, in the coping mechanisms of teachers on the challenges encountered in the new normal during a pandemic, three themes emerged from the re-

sponses of the participants, which included managing time wisely, establishing a professional circle, and seeking help from teacher mentors. These themes implied that teachers understood that time management was an important practice to meet home and work demands. It helped them accomplish things on time, attend school duties, do household chores, and regain energy through rest. On the other hand, educational insights were learned from the study findings. Three themes also emerged from the responses of the participants: that teaching was a challenging task, establishing a professional circle was needed, and seeking help from a teacher mentor was beneficial. These themes implied

Fig. 5. Emerging Themes On The Educational Insights Learned From The Experiences Of The Informants

that teaching is an effortful task, especially in higher education, because lesson content should be based on research and theories to create and develop the student's scientific competence. Education shall offer relevant content and teaching and critical and analyzing competence. The themes also highlighted that the mentor's love of the profession was just one way they could share a love of learning; they would also get

to delve into new topics and learn right along with the children. Added to this is collaboration, which generally was the strong support among teachers. It involved the sharing of ideas and skills in order to achieve a common goal. Working collaboratively instead of individually helps improve productivity and give teachers a sense of purpose in teaching.

4.2. Implications—This research provided an understanding of the experiences, coping mechanisms, and educational insights learned by local college instructors in the new normal of teaching during a pandemic. Data obtained had implications for various educational stakeholders, including policymakers, administrators, and teachers. The implications of the practice of this study were as follows: Policy Makers To meet teachers' needs as they undergo new normal teaching during the pandemic. Ultimately, this would benefit students, schools, and education in general. Moreover, the quality and appropriateness of support for teachers in the new normal teaching during a pandemic, the supportiveness of the work environment, and the use of appropriate enhancement, policies, and practices that determine how teachers were able to continuously perform their duties and functions as learning facilitators during the new normal learning. School Principals To foster stimulating social and professional conditions

for career and mutual development for teachers and to influence the change of attitude as a teacher's own mechanism in implementing the new normal during a pandemic, and the development and promotion of students and society as a whole. Policymakers may create tripartite (teachers, principals, and supervisors) truly collaborative system policies in the implementation of new standard teaching for the teacher's capability building that could bring the highest impact on the educational practices of teachers. School principals and supervisors could work more than ever so that the attention given to the teachers on new normal teaching is truly meaningful and fruitful. They should focus on staff emotional, health, and skills development in pursuit of improving teaching capability even during the pandemic. Teachers To nurture meaningful relationships, continuous emotional, physical, and skills development among teachers, and maintain a positive and stimulating classroom climate in the new normal of teaching.

4.3. Future Directions—Some areas for future studies within this field need to be explored. Further development on the similar and different contexts can be done in this study. It is recommended that teachers and educators at different education levels, such as junior, senior high, tertiary level, or vocational level, consider other

perspectives on implementing the new normal teaching during the COVID-19 crisis. Another suggestion was to conduct a case study featuring a specific case of teachers dealing with the challenges of new normal teaching. This would yield advantageous findings and implications tailored to the organization and hierarchical context of the education sector.

5. References

- Al-Dosari, H. (2011). Faculty members and students perceptions of e-learning in the english department: A project evaluation. *J. Soc. Sci.*, 7, 391–407.
- Alexander, S. (2010). Flexible learning in higher education. In *International encyclopedia of education* (pp. 441–447). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-08-044894-7.00868-x>
- Ali, N. (2020). Students disappointed with online teaching system amid covid-19 [Accessed: 2025-02-02].
- Ali, W. (2020). Online and remote learning in higher education institutes: A necessity in light of covid-19 pandemic. *Higher Education Studies*, 10(3), 16–25. <https://doi.org/10.5539/hes.v10n3p16>
- Anaraki, F. (2004). Developing an effective and efficient elearning platform. *Int. J. Comput. Internet Manag.*, 12, 57–63.
- Arkorful, V., & Abaidoo, N. (2014). The role of e-learning, the advantages and disadvantages of its adoption in higher education. *Int. J. Educ. Res.*, 2, 397–410.
- Babu, D., & Sridevi, D. (2018). Importance of e-learning in higher education: A study. *Int. J. Res. Cult. Soc.*, 2, 84–88.
- Bakia, M., Shear, L., Toyama, Y., & Lassetter, A. (2012). *Understanding the implications of online learning for educational productivity*. Office of Educational Technology, US Department of Education.
- Basilaia, G., & Kvavadze, D. (2020). Transition to online education in schools during a sars-cov-2 coronavirus (covid-19) pandemic in georgia. *Pedagogical Research*, 5(4), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.29333/pr/7937>
- Benta, D., Bologna, G., & Dzitac, I. (2014). E-learning platforms in higher education: Case study. *Procedia Comput. Sci.*, 31, 1170–1176.
- Bijeesh, N. (2017). Advantages and disadvantages of distance learning [Accessed: 2020-09-10].
- Borup, J. (2016). Teacher perceptions of parental engagement at a cyber high school. *Journal of Research in Technology in Education*, 48(2), 67–83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2016.1146560>
- Borup, J., West, R. E., Graham, C. R., & Davies, R. S. (2014). The adolescent community of engagement framework: A lens for research on k-12 online learning. *Journal of Technology and Teacher Education*, 22(1), 107–129.
- Brown, C. (2017). Advantages and disadvantages of distance learning [Accessed: 2020-09-10].
- Cacheiro-Gonzalez, M., Medina-Rivilla, A., Dominguez-Garrido, M., & Medina-Dominguez, M. (2019). The learning platform in distance higher education: Student’s perceptions. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 20, 71–95.
- Cannon, R. (2000). Guide to support the implementation of the learning and teaching plan year 2000 [Australia: The University of Adelaide].
- Cantoni, V., Cellario, M., & Porta, M. (2004). Perspectives and challenges in e-learning: Towards natural interaction paradigms. *Journal of Visual Languages and Computing*, 15, 333–345.
- Cheung, C., & Cable, J. (2017). Eight principles of effective online teaching: A decade-long lessons learned in project management education. *Project Management World Journal*, 6, 1–16.
- Clark, R., & Mayer, R. (2016). *E-learning and the science of instruction* (4th). Wiley.

- Cleofas, J. (2020). Life interruptions, learnings, and hopes among filipino college students during covid-19 pandemic. *European Journal of Teacher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2020.1820981>
- Coburn, C., Russell, J., Kaufman, J., & Stein, M. (2012). Supporting sustainability: Teachers' advice networks and ambitious instructional reform. *American Journal of Education*, *119*, 137–182. <https://doi.org/10.1086/667699>
- Cohen, E., & Nycz, M. (2006). Learning objects and e-learning: An informing science perspective. *Interdisciplinary Journal of E-Skills and Lifelong Learning*, *2*, 23–34.
- Cohen, J., & Kupferschmidt, K. (2020). Countries test tactics in 'war' against covid-19. *Science*, *367*(6484), 1287–1288. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.367.6484.1287>
- Collado, Z. (2022). Embracing the “new normal”: Exploring readiness among filipino students to engage in virtual classes. *Journal of Educational Technology and Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23735082.2022.203228>
- Costa, C., Alvelos, H., & Teixeira, L. (2012). The use of moodle e-learning platform: A study in a portuguese university. *Procedia Technology*, *5*, 334–343.
- Dagger, D., O'Connor, A., Lawless, S., Walsh, E., & Wade, V. (2007). Service-oriented e-learning platforms: From monolithic systems to flexible services. *IEEE Internet Comput.*, *11*, 28–35. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MIC.2007.93>
- Dai, D., & Lin, G. (2020). Online home study plan for postponed 2020 spring semester during the covid-19 epidemic: A case study of tangquan middle school in nanjing, jiangsu province, china. *Best Evidence in Chinese Education*, *4*(2), 543–.
- Davis, L. N., Gough, M., & Taylor, L. L. (2019). Online teaching: Advantages, obstacles and tools for getting it right. *Journal of Teaching in Travel & Tourism*, *19*(3), 256–263. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15313220.2019.1668969>
- Davis, M. (2000). Time and the nursing home assistant: Relations among time management, perceived control over time, and work-related outcomes. *Academy of Management, Toronto*.
- Dhull, P., & Sakshi, M. (2017). Online learning. *International Educational Research Journal*, *3*, 32–34.
- Dwivedi, Y., Hughes, L., Coombs, C., Constantiou, I., Duan, Y., Edwards, J., et al. (2020). Impact of covid-19 pandemic on information management research and practice: Transforming education, work, and life. *International Journal of Information Management*, *55*, 102211. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2020.102211>
- Eilam, B., & Aharon, I. (2003). Students planning in the process of self-regulated learning. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, *28*, 304–314. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0361-476X\(02\)00042-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0361-476X(02)00042-5)
- Engelbrecht, E. (2005). Adapting to changing expectations: Post-graduate students' experience of an e-learning tax program. *Computers in Education*, *45*, 217–229.
- Eyles, A., Gibbons, S., & Montebruno, P. (2020). Covid-19 school shutdowns: What will they do to our children's education? [Available online: <http://cep.lse.ac.uk/pubs/download/cepcovid-19-001.pdf>]. *A CEP Covid-19 analysis Briefing note No. 001*.
- Feng, L., & Cavanaugh, C. (2011). Success in online high school biology: Factors influencing student academic performance. *The Quarterly Review of Distance Education*, *12*(1), 37–54.

- Fischer, H., Heise, L., Heinz, M., Moebius, K., & Koehler, T. (2014). E-learning trends and hypes in academic teaching. methodology and findings of a trend study. *Proceedings of the International Association for Development of the Information Society (IADIS) International Conference on Cognition and Exploratory Learning in the Digital Age (CELDA)*, 63–69.
- Frederick, B. J. A., & Stephen, O. O. (2010). Teachers’ perceptions of staff development programmes as it relates to teachers’ effectiveness: A study of rural primary schools in kenya. *Educational Research & Review*, 5(1).
- Gallie, K., & Joubert, D. (2004). Paradigm shift: From traditional to online education. *Studies in Learning, Evaluation, Innovation, and Development*, 1, 32–36.
- Goodall, J. (2016). Technology and school–home communication. *International Journal of Pedagogies & Learning*, 11, 118–131. <https://doi.org/10.1080/22040552.2016.1227252>
- Gordon, N. (2014). *Flexible pedagogies: Technology-enhanced learning*. The Higher Education Academy.
- Gosling, D., & Moon, J. (2001). *How to use learning outcomes and assessment criteria*. SEEC Office.
- Hillman, D., Willis, D., & Gunawardena, C. (1994). Learner-interface interaction in distance education: An extension of contemporary models and strategies for practitioners. *American Journal of Distance Education*, 8(2), 30–24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08923649409526853>
- Hollingworth, S., Mansaray, A., Allen, K., & Rose, A. (2011). Parents’ perspectives on technology and children’s learning in the home: Social class and the role of the habitus. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 27, 347–360.
- Horton, W. (2006). *E-learning by design*. Pfeiffer.
- Huang, R., Liu, D., Tlili, A., Yang, J., Wang, H., et al. (2020). *Handbook on facilitating flexible learning during educational disruption: The chinese experience in maintaining undisturbed learning in covid-19 outbreak*. Smart Learning Institute of Beijing Normal University.
- Hunt, J. (2008). Nurturing children’s natural love of learning [Accessed 1/8/08].
- Inoue, Y. (Ed.). (2007). *Online education for lifelong learning*. IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-59904-319-7>
- Jahangir, S., Saheen, N., & Kazmi, S. (2012). In-service training: A contributory factor influencing teachers’ performance. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 1.
- Jinshan, H. (2020). Parents grapple with e-learning as chinese schools stay shut.
- Jogan, S. (2019). *Self-learning module in the achievement and retention of higher secondary students in english* [Doctoral dissertation].
- Kazmi, S., Pervez, T., & Mumtaz, S. (2011). In-service teacher training in pakistan schools and total quality management. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research In Business*.
- Kemp, J., & Smelie, J. (1989). *Planning, producing and using instructional media*. Harper Row.
- Ko, S., & Rossen, S. (2017). *Teaching online: A practical guide*. Routledge.
- Koohang, A., & Harman, K. (2005). Open source: A metaphor for e-learning. *Information Science Journal*, 8, 75–86.

- Krishnamurthy, S. (2020). The future of business education: A commentary in the shadow of the covid-19 pandemic. *Journal of Business Research*, 117, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.05.034>
- Lay, C., & Schouwenburg, H. (2003). Trait procrastination, time management, and academic behavior. *Journal of Social Behavior and Personality*, 8, 647–662.
- Lee, M., & Figueroa, R. (2012). Internal and external indicators of virtual learning success a guide to success in k-12 virtual learning. *Distance Learning*, 9(1), 21–28.
- Liguori, E., & Winkler, C. (2020). From offline to online: Challenges and opportunities for entrepreneurship education following the covid-19 pandemic. *Entrepreneurship Education and Pedagogy*, 3(4), 346–351. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2515127420916738>
- Lines, R. (2004). Influence of participation in strategic change: Resistance, organizational commitment and change goal achievement. *Journal of Change Management*, 4(3), 193–215. <http://taylorandfrancis.metapress.com/>
- Llego, M. (2020). Deped learning delivery modalities for school year 2020-2021.
- Makrooni, G. (2019). Being a first-generation migrant family student in finland: Perceptions and experiences of the educational journey to higher education. *Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies*, 6(3), 157–170. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejecs/293>
- Martín-Blas, T., & Serrano-Fernández, A. (2009). The role of new technologies in the learning process: Moodle as a teaching tool in physics. *Computers & Education*, 52, 35–44.
- Materna, L. (2007). *Jump start the adult learner: How to engage and motivate adults using brain-compatible strategies*. Corwin Press.
- McCombs, B., & Whistler, J. (2007). *The learner centered classroom and school: Strategies for increasing student motivation and achievement*. Jossey-Bass Publishers.
- McLeod, S. (2007). Do schools quash students' enthusiasm for learning? [accessed 25/7/08]. www.techlearning.com/blog/2007/03/do_schools_quash_students_enth.php
- Mershon, K. (2018). A pedagogy of vulnerability: The craft of teaching in the academic study of religion. <https://craftofteachingreligion.wordpress.com/2018/10/22/a-pedagogy-ofvulnerability>
- Montacute, R. (2020). Social mobility and covid-19 [accessed 30 July 2020]. <https://www.suttontrust.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/COVID-19-and-Social-Mobility-1.pdf>
- Moore, M. G. (1983). The individual adult learner. In M. Tight (Ed.), *Adult learning and education*. Croom Helm.
- Moore, M. G. (1997). *Theory of transactional distance* (D. Keegan, Ed.). Routledge.
- Morrison, A. P. (2020). Online teaching placements during covid-19 pandemic in chile: Challenges and opportunities.
- Nafisah, S. B., Alamery, A. H., Al Nafesa, A., Aleid, B., & Brazanji, N. A. (2018). School closure during novel influenza: A systematic review. *Journal of Infection and Public Health*, 11(5), 657–661. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jiph.2018.01.003>
- Nagrle, P. (2013). Advantages and disadvantages of distance education [accessed 10 September 2020]. <https://surejob.in/advantages-anddisadvantages-of-distance-education.html>
- Navarro, P., & Shoemaker, J. (2000). Performance and perceptions of distance learners in cyberspace. *American Journal of Distance Education*, 14, 15–35.

- Nillsen, R. (2004). Can the love of learning be taught? [accessed 24/7/08]. *Journal of University Teaching and Learning Practice*, 1(1), 1–9. http://jutlp.uow.edu.au/2004_v01_i01/pdf/nilsen.001.pdf
- Nycz, M., & Cohen, E. B. (2007). The basics for understanding e-learning (N. A. Buzzetto-More, Ed.), 1–17.
- OECD. (2020a). Education disrupted – education rebuilt: Some insights from pisa on the availability and use of digital tools for learning. <https://oecdeditoday.com/coronavirus-education-digital-tools-forlearning/>
- OECD. (2020b). How can teachers and school systems respond to the covid-19 pandemic? some lessons from talis. <https://oecdeditoday.com/how-teachers-schoolsystems-respond-coronavirus-talis/>
- of Education, D. (2020a). Memoranda related to covid-19.
- of Education, D. (2020b). Official statement department of education.
- of Education, D. (2020c). Policy guideline for the provision of learning resources in the implementation of learning continuity plan [Department of Education Order 18 s. 2020].
- of Health, D. (2020). Department of health phehrman, m. [Psychological factors and distance education.].
- Ogbonna, C. G., Ibezim, N. E., & Obi, C. A. (2019). Synchronous versus asynchronous e-learning in teaching word processing: An experimental approach. *South African Journal of Education*, 39(2), 1–9.
- on Higher Education, C. (2020). Covid-19 updates - advisory 6.
- Oproiu, G. (2015). A study about using e-learning platform (moodle) in university teaching process. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 180, 426–432.
- Orpen, C. (2004). The effect of time-management training on employee attitudes and behaviour: A field experiment. *The Journal of Psychology*, 128, 393–396. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00223980.1994.9712743>
- Oswald, S., Mossholder, K., & Harris, S. (1994). Vision salience and strategic involvement: Implications for psychological attachment to organization and job. *Strategic Management Journal*, 15(6), 477–490.
- Ouadoud, M., Chkouri, M., & Nejjari, A. (2018). Learning management system and the underlying learning theories: Towards a new modeling of an lms. *International Journal of Information Science*, 2, 25–33.
- Oye, N., Salleh, M., & Iahad, N. (2012). E-learning methodologies and tools. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 3, 48–52.
- Oztok, M., Zingaro, D., Brett, C., & Hewitt, J. (2013). Exploring asynchronous and synchronous tool use in online courses. *Computers Education*, 60, 87–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2012.08.007>
- Papachristos, D., Arvanitis, K., Vassilakis, K., Kalogiannakis, M., Kikilias, P., & Zafeiri, E. (2010). An educational model for asynchronous e-learning. a case study in a higher technology education. *International Journal of Advanced Corporate Learning*, 3(1), 32–36.
- Parnell, J., & Crandall, W. (2003). Propensity for participative decision making, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, organizational citizenship behavior, and intentions to leave among egyptian managers. *Multinational Business Review*, 11(1), 45–65. <http://proquest.umi.com/>

- Penuel, W., Fishman, B., Yamaguchi, R., & Gallagher, L. (2007). What makes professional development effective? strategies that foster curriculum implementation. *American Educational Research Journal*, 44, 921–958. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831207308221>
- Petrie, C. (2020). Spotlight: Quality education for all during covid-19 crisis (hundred research report 01) [United Nations, Available at: <https://hundred.org/en/collections/qualityeducation-for-all-during-coronavirus>]. <https://doi.org/10.5194/se-2020-20-ac1>
- Povey, J., Campbell, A. K., Willis, L.-D., Haynes, M., Western, M., Bennett, S., Antrobus, E., & Pedde, C. (2016). Engaging parents in schools and building parent-school partnerships: The role of school and parent organization leadership. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 79, 128–141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2016.07.005>
- Quinones, M. T. (2020). Deped clarifies blended, distance learning modalities for sy 2020-2021 [Philippine Information Agency, Available at: <https://pia.gov.ph/news/articles/1046619>].
- Sadeghi, M. (2019). A shift from classroom to distance learning: Advantages and limitations. *Int. J. Res. Engl. Educ.*, 4, 80–88. <https://doi.org/10.7575/aiac.ijree.v.4n.2p.80>
- Sahu, P. (2020). Closure of universities due to coronavirus disease 2019 (covid-19): Impact on education and mental health of students and academic staff. *Cureus*, 12(4), e7541. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.7541>
- Sax, B. (2006). Learning the love of learning: Newman’s ideal updated. *Liberal Arts Online*, 1–4. <https://www.wabash.edu/cila/docs/Apr06Learning%20theLove.PDF>
- Selwyn, N., Banaji, S., Hadjithoma-Garstka, C., & Clark, W. (2011). Providing a platform for parents? exploring the nature of parental engagement with school learning platforms. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 27(4), 314–323. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2729.2011.00428.x>
- Simmie, G. M. (2007). Teacher design teams (tdts) – building capacity for innovation, learning and curriculum implementation in the continuing professional development of in-career teachers. *Irish Educational Studies*, 26, 163–176. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03323310701295914>
- Singh, V., & Thurman, A. (2019). How many ways can we define online learning? a systematic literature review of definitions of online learning (1988-2018). *American Journal of Distance Education*, 33(4), 289–306. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08923647.2019.1663082>
- Slaven, G., & Totterdell, P. (2003). Time management training: Does it transfer to the workplace? *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 8, 20–28. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02683949310024432>
- Somech, A., & Bogler, R. (2002). Antecedents and consequences of teacher organizational and professional commitment. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 38(4), 555–577. <http://ejournals.ebsco.com/>
- Song, L., Singleton, E. S., Hill, J. R., & Koh, M. H. (2004). Improving online learning: Student perceptions of useful and challenging characteristics. *Internet and Higher Education*, 7(1), 59–70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2003.11.003>
- Stead, E. A., & Starmer, C. F. (2003). Restoring the joy in learning.
- Stern, B. (2004). A comparison of online and face-to-face instruction in an undergraduate foundations of american education course. *Contemp. Issues Technol. Teach. Educ. CITE J.*, 4, 196–213.
- Sturm, E., & Quaynor, L. (2020). A window, mirror, and wall: How educators use twitter for professional learning. *Research in Social Sciences and Technology*, 5(1), 22–44. <https://doi.org/10.46303/ressat.05.01.2>

- Sutton, L. A. (2001). The principle of vicarious interaction in computer-mediated communications. *International Journal of Educational Telecommunications*, 7(3), 223–242. <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/9534/>
- Tham, C., & Werner, J. (2005). Designing and evaluating e-learning in higher education: A review and recommendations. *J. Leadersh. Organ. Stud.*, 11, 15–25.
- Tria, J. Z. (2020, June). The covid-19 pandemic through the lens of education in the philippines: The new normal.
- UNESCO. (2020a). Covid-19 educational disruption and response.
- UNESCO. (2020b). Covid-19 educational disruption and response.
- UNESCO. (2020c, February). How is china ensuring learning when classes are disrupted by coronavirus? <https://en.unesco.org/news/how-china-ensuring-learning-when-classes-are-disrupted-coronavirus>
- Vescio, V., Ross, D., & Adams, A. (2008). A review of research on the impact of professional learning communities on teaching practice and student learning. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 24, 80–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2007.01.004>
- Viner, R., Russell, S., Croker, H., Packer, J., Ward, J., Stansfield, C., & Booy, R. (2020). School closure and management practices during coronavirus outbreaks including covid-19: A rapid systematic review. *Lancet Child Adolesc Health*, 4, 397–404. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-4642\(20\)30095-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-4642(20)30095-X)
- Voogt, J., Westbroek, H., Handelzalts, A., Walraven, A., McKenney, S., Pieters, J., & De Vries, B. (2011). Teacher learning in collaborative curriculum design. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 27, 1235–1244. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2011.07.003>
- Weimer, M. (2002). *Learner-centered teaching: Five key changes to practice*. Jossey-Bass Publishers.
- WHO (World Health Organization). (2019). Guidelines on physical activity, sedentary behaviour and sleep for children under 5 years of age. <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/311664>
- Wilder-Smith, A., & Freedman, D. (2020). Isolation, quarantine, social distancing and community containment: Pivotal role for old-style public health measures in the novel coronavirus (2019-ncov) outbreak. *J. Travel. Med.*, 27. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jtm/taaa020>
- World Bank. (2020). Remote learning, distance education and online learning during the covid-19 pandemic: A resource list by the world bank’s edtech team (english). <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/964121585254860581/Remote-Learning-Distance-Education-and-Online-Learning-During-the-COVID19-Pandemic-A-Resource-List-by-the-World-Banks-Edtech-Team>
- Worldometers. (2020). Coronavirus cases [Accessed on April 25, 2020]. <https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/>
- Yousafzai, A. (2020). Low-cost private schools may not be able to survive the covid-19 crisis. <https://www.thenews.com.pk/print/637486-low-cost-private-schools-may-not-be-able-to-survive-covid-19-crisis>
- Zhang, W., Wang, Y., Yang, L., & Wang, C. H. (2020). Suspending classes without stopping learning: China’s education emergency management policy in the covid-19 outbreak. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 13(58), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm13030055>